

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

Deliverable 8.5. Participants toolkit

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP8
Deliverable no. & title	D8.5. Participants toolkit
Version	V1
Creation Date	06.06.2018
Last change	
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Dissemination level	<input type="checkbox"/> PU-Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP- Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO- Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	AWI (partner 1)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - NPI, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - ULAVAL, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UAF/CFOS, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 – AP, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 – CSIC-UTM, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – IOPAN, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – FMI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – DTU-AQUA
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Deliverable No. 8.5

Participants toolkit

A Participants' 'toolkit' for the ARICE consortium has been set up and is available at the internal ARICE website (<https://arice.eu/intranet/documents>). Every consortium partner has got a login key and a password to access the internal website.

The Participants' 'toolkit' folder contains partner lists, presentations and promotional material, templates for deliverables, presentations, etc. as seen below. The folder will be continuously updated during the life-time of the project.

Sicher | <https://arice.eu/intranet/documents>

Home About News Outreach Apply for Ship Time Intranet

Intranet / Documents

Documents

Documents (consortium only)
ARICE Grant Agreement (pdf)

ARICE Partners
General partner list (xlsx)
Work Packages - mailing lists (xlsx)

ARICE - Presentations and promotional material
ARICE short info (pptx)
ARICE call for proposals 2018 (pptx)
ARICE poster (pdf)
ARICE brochure (pdf)

ARICE - Templates
Deliverable template (doc)
PPT base for widescreen (pptx)
PPT base for regularsize (pptx)

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